

InterAgency Institute
BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

2023 ANNUAL REPORT

IA Board - 2023.

February, 2024.

Presentation

Founded in 2020 exclusively by women, the InterAgency Institute (IA) is a digital think tank and collective of researchers from the Global South based in 7 different countries. Our mission is to support the exchange of knowledge, ideas, and perspectives from the Global South. We are committed to creating an inclusive research environment that prioritizes the knowledge and insights of those who have been traditionally excluded from research and policy conversations.

The IA aims at developing research for the benefit of policy building and enhancement, advancing the importance of interagency cooperation in the various levels of society development. This effort concentrates on two main areas of research: Global Security and Local Development. The IA researches and advocates for security & social policy agendas that affect human rights and human-being, valuing a human-centered approach.

Our main publication product is the IA Policy Brief Series, registered under the ISSN 2789-8040. Our other publications include Reports and Glossary, all part of our ZENODO library, under the European Union OPEN AIRE base.

This document summarizes all activities and publications produced by the InterAgency researchers throughout the 2023 year.

January

- Statement of Repudiation to the anti-democratic act in Brazil on January 08th;
- Policy Brief “Brazil and Environmental Protection: Discourse and Policy for a National System” (Rita Feodrippe - USP);
- Exchange of knowledge with the “Rete Italiana Pace e Disarmo,” under the Stop Killer Robots (SKR) Campaign, about achieving parliamentarians with the small and middle states discussion on nuclear power policy (Ana Paula Rodriguez & Sabrina Medeiros);

February

- Policy Brief “The Expansion of the Debate on the Regulation of Autonomous Weapons in Iberofonia” (Ana Paula Rodriguez & Juliana Martins);
- Acceptance as a Member of the International Committee of the World Forum on Human Rights (Buenos Aires, Argentina - March 2023);
- Policy Brief “Peacekeeping Operation Training as a Cooperation between Brazil and Sweden” (Carolina Ambinder).
- Participation in the Global Futures Forum/United Nations (UN) in the Groups “Peace and Security,” “UN Governance Innovation,” and “Development,” supporting its proposals (Sabrina Medeiros);

March

- Policy Brief “The Complex Problem of Free and Open Indo-Pacific Initiative: Japan’s role in defending the region” (Diogo Amaral);
- Participation at the meeting of the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) for the review of the 2022 Report on Trafficking in Persons (Ana Paula Rodriguez);
- Policy Brief “Women, Peace, and Security Agenda: Perspectives for Brazil” (Cintiene Sandes);
- Participation in the meeting for the organization of the I Interparliamentary Debate on Artificial Intelligence applied to Defense in Iberophony (Ana Paula Rodrigues, Juliana Martins & Luís Campani);
- Participation in the Global Futures Forum/UN, in the Environmental Governance Thematic Track (Ana Beatriz Costa & Luzia Becker);

April

- Participation in the UNODC’s training for being a stakeholder at the WhatsOn platform (Sabrina Medeiros);
- Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with Accord University (Somalia) to provide classes for the Master of Public Administration;
- Policy Brief “The Limits to Artificial Intelligence: Do Machines Have Ethical Bias?” (Danielle Ayres & Rafael Mota - UNIFOR);
- Seminar “Introduction to Public Policies” (Ana Beatriz Duarte) for the Master of Public Administration from Accord University;
- Policy Brief “Migración en el Mar Mediterráneo: una Mirada a las Conyunturas Diversas y Operaciones Interagenciales” (Daniele Dionísio & Ana Paula Rodriguez);
- Seminar “Trade Policy” (Silvana Schimanski) for the Master of Public Administration from Accord University;

May

- Seminar “Public Policies & Defence” (Carolina Ambinder) for the Master of Public Administration from Accord University;
- Seminar “International System & Geopolitics: How does it affect Public Policy?” (Larlecciane Piccolli) for the Master of Public Administration from Accord University;
- Policy Brief “Innovation in Defence: Challenges and Possibilities for the Brazilian System” (Ana Luiza Paiva & Karina Rodrigues - ECEME);
- Seminar “Local Development Policies: Tourism & Heritage” (Luzia Becker & Ana Clara Simões) for the Master of Public Administration from Accord University;
- Participation at the Luxembourg Autonomous Weapons Systems Conference under the SKR Campaign (Luís Campani);
- Seminar “Identifying Megatrends: Planning Future Policies” (Verônica Pires) for the Master of Public Administration from Accord University;
- Presentation of a statement at the 2nd Session of the 2023 Group of Governmental Experts (GGE) about emerging technologies in the area of lethal autonomous weapons systems (LAWS) under the Convention on Conventional Weapons (Luís Campani);
- Policy Brief “AI Summer: Alerts and Proposals on the Regulation of Smart Tools and Lethal Weapons Systems (LAWS)” (Juliana Martins);
- Seminar “Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems” (Ana Beatriz Duarte & Luís Campani) for the Master of Public Administration from Accord University;

June

- Report on the 2nd Session of the 2023 GGE about emerging technologies in the area of LAWS under the Convention on Conventional Weapons (Luís Campani);
- Policy Brief “Nuclear Weapons and Autonomous Systems: Even Closer to Midnight?” (Larlecciane Piccolli);
- Endorsement to the “Nuclear Taboo, from Norm to Law” Declaration from the G20 countries;
- Policy Brief “The CCW Review Process within Arms-Producers and Non-Producers” (Sabrina Medeiros & Ítalo Poty - UFRJ).

July

- Publication of the Consultancy for the International Organization for Migration (IOM) (Ana Paula Rodriguez & Felipe Neves - Plataforma Cipó);
- Endorsement of the list of principles by UNA-UK, Plataforma Cipó, and Strategy for Humanity for fair, inclusive, transparent appointments for UN senior leaders;
- Policy Brief “Decoding Unpredictability: the Debate on Predictability for Policy Considerations on Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems” (Luís Campani);
- Contribution to the Cyber Programme of Action (PoA) of the Paris Call as one of its supporters (Danielle Ayres & Sabrina Medeiros);
- Participation at the European Workshops in International Studies (EISA) 2023, in Amsterdam, with the papers “Multi-level Governance and Interagency Cooperation: Experiences to Build and Integrate Security” (Daniele Dionísio & Ana Paula Rodriguez) and “From Mining Policy to Water (in) Security of the Territories: the Interagency Consultation and the Role of the State in defense of Regenerative Development” (Luzia Becker);
- Policy Brief “From Mining Policy to Water (in) Security of the Territories: the Interagency Consultation and the Role of the State in the Defence of Regenerative Development” (Luzia Becker).

August

- Policy Brief “New Technologies and Artificial Intelligence: Can we Change the Reality of the Poorest Countries?” (Lygia Hryniewicz);
- Policy Brief “Challenges of InterAgency Cooperation in the Context of the Trade Facilitation Agreement and the Sustainable Development Goals” (Silvana Schimanski).

September

- Policy Brief “Addressing the Intersection of Human Trafficking and Drug Trafficking: Initial Considerations on Interagency Cooperation Scale” (Verônica Pires);
- Participation with a statement at the 14th Working Group on International Cooperation of the UNODC (Carolina Ambinder, Sabrina Medeiros & Victor Gaspar Filho);
- Policy Brief “Deep-Sea Mining and the Responsibility of International Players Towards Environmental Preservation” (Victor Gaspar Filho);
- Participation at the “Global People’s Assembly”/UN, in New York City, in the activities “Intergeneration Dialogue” and the preparation for the “Summit of Future” (Raquel Castilho).

October

- Policy Brief: “Turkey and International Defence Cooperation: the Position in the North Atlantic Treaty Organisation (NATO) and the Ambition for the European Union (EU)” (Allan Antunes, Carolina Ambinder & João Pedro Mendonça - UniLaSalle- RJ);
- Participation at the meeting “Constructive Dialogues on Trafficking in Persons” from the Review Mechanism of the United Nations Convention Against Transnational Organized Crime (UNTOC) (Beatriz Costa & Luzia Becker);
- Participation at the events “Emerging Global Politics and the United Nations,” promoted by C4UN We Need, and a roundtable discussion on the UN Day to restart the “Road to the Summit” series (Raquel Castilho);
- Participation at high-level events at the United Nations (UN) New York Headquarters: "Global People's Assembly," "Inclusive Global Governance for a Peaceful and Resilient World," "Sustainability Summit NYC 2023" & "Global Forum of Communities Discriminated on Work and Descent" (GFOD), (Raquel Castilho);
- Signature of the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA) Statement First Committee on Disarmament and International Security about the War on Ukraine.

November

- Policy Brief “Why We Need a Multilateral and Global Understanding of Artificial Intelligence (AI): the Case of the Symbolic/Connectionist Controversy (Ana Beatriz Duarte IA);
- Participation at the “24-Hour Conference on Global Organized Crimes” from the “Global Initiative Against Transnational Organized Crime,” with the presentation “Interagency on Human Trafficking” (Beatriz Costa & Luzia Becker);
- Policy Brief “Environmental Education for Regenerative Development” (Luzia Becker & Ana Clara Simões);
- Participation in the 6th Paris Peace Forum, in the Cyber & Artificial Intelligence Nexus (Ana Beatriz Duarte & Sabrina Medeiros);
- Policy Brief “The International Regime for the Protection of Stateless Persons and the Recognition of their Legal Status in Brazilian Legislation” (Joyce Souza);

December

- Policy Brief “Operation Acolhida and the Main Challenges in Interagency Cooperation” (Ana Luiza Paiva);
- Policy Brief “The Use of Cyberspace and Interagency Action in the Prevention-Elimination of Human Trafficking” (Luzia Becker & Marta Beatriz Costa).

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